

Internship Report

On

Human Resource Planning and Recruitment Process of Dan Foods Ltd.

Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University

Trishal, Mymensingh.

Internship Report

On

Human Resource Planning and Recruitment Process of Dan Foods Ltd.

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Session: - 2017-18

Department of Human Resource Management

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Letter of Transmittal

March 01, 2023

To,

Mahmudul Hasan Pias

Lecturer

Department of Human Resource Management

Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University

Trishal, Mymensingh

Subject: Submission of Internship Report on “**Human Resource Planning and Recruitment Process of Dan Food Ltd.**”

Dear Sir,

Here is my Internship report on “**Human Resource Planning and Recruitment Process of Dan food Ltd.**” A study on Dan Food Ltd that you have assigned me to submit as a partial requirement for the course in Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA). This Course gave me opportunities to collect my theoretical knowledge with the corporate culture. I have collected what I believe to be the most relevant information as quite as authentic. I have tried my level to make the best effective report. I must mention that I am extremely thankful to you for the guidance and attention of yours whenever is required.

May I therefore wish and hope that you would accept my effort and oblige thereby.

Sincerely Yours,

Md. Monwarul Islam Furat

ID- 18133010

Registration No- 7406

Session- 2017-18

Department of Human Resource Management

Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University

Trishal, Mymensingh

Student Declaration

I am Md. Monwarul Islam Furat, student of BBA (Bachelor of Business Administration), Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University. Here I am declared that the report title “**Human Resource Planning and Recruitment process of Dan Food Ltd.** While preparing the report I didn’t copyright act Intentionally. The total Report done by me under the supervision of **Mahmudul Hasan Pias**, Faculty of Business Administration of Jatiya Kazi Nazrul Islam University.

I also confirm that, the Internship Report is only prepared for my academic requirement not for any other purposes.

Sincerely Yours,

Md. Monwarul Islam Furat

ID- 18133010

Registration No- 7406

Session- 2017-18

Department of Human Resource Management

Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University

Trishal, Mymensingh

Supervisor Declaration

This is to certify that the internship report on “**Human Resource Planning and Recruitment Process: A study on Dan Foods Ltd.**” has been submitted partially for fulfillment the internship course for the degree of Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) at Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University carried out by the **Md. Monwarul Islam Furat**, the student of Human Resource Management under my supervision his ID No: **18133010**, Registration No:**7406** and Session:**2017-18**.

As far as I know, he tried his best to submit the internship report successfully and I believe this study will help him in the future to build up his career.

He is granted to submit his Internship Report.

Wish him for the best success in life.

Mahmudul Hasan Pias

Lecturer

Department of Human Resource Management

Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University

Trishal, Mymensingh

Acknowledgement

First of all, I would like to thank Almighty Allah for his grace in accomplishing my internship report on time.

I would like to express my post gratitude to my academic supervisor **Mahmudul Hasan Pias** from the core of my heart for his kind support, guidance, constructive supervision, instructions, advice and for motivating me to do this report.

I am also thankful to my Internship Supervisor **Mr. Shibli Ahmed the HR Corporate Lead of Dan Foods Ltd** for supervising me and providing various key information and giving me the path to write a fruitful report. I would also like to give special thanks to **Mr. Zakir Polash, Recruitment Associate of Dan Foods Limited, Sartaj Rahman, Sales Support Officer and Soikot Barua, Executive IT** who was there from the till the end of my internship. They supported me and taught me so many things. The team members of Recruitment and Selection team were so helpful to me I am grateful to them.

Finally, an honorable mention goes to my families and friends and the fellow interns for their understandings and for supporting me in completing this report. Without the help of the particular that mentioned above, I would have faced some difficulties while doing this report.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report is totally based on experience and knowledge that has been gathered information throughout the internship program offered at Dan Foods Ltd. The report helps me to generate more ideas knowledge about the Human Resource planning and the overall recruitment process in the company. Moved on different jobs fair and then there participated in the amount of learnings and managed whatever learned by working as a HR Intern at Dan Foods Ltd. As a HR Intern directly worked on to the HR activities. In this Report try to discuss how Dan Foods Ltd do their HR activities and Recruitment Process. During Internship tenure tried to get depth knowledge about the HR function and the recruitment process and find the mistakes or gap analysis that creates problems in the areas of HR activities but giving some recommendations helps them to make the working activities far better. In the recruitment process tried to discuss about the overall HRM Planning in organization works and How Dan Foods Ltd company recruit candidates or shortlisted process of collecting best select talented candidates. During Internship while preparing the report need to face some challenges like time limitation, work pressure etc. but learned through many processes by working on to it. The responsibility whatever the management give me the tasks completed the task fully and actual tasks and activities helps me to enhance my learning a lot. Some recommendations for the Dan foods Ltd. of this report helps me to reflect how the Dan Foods Ltd can perform much better to have a sustainable to retain employees for long run.

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Chapter-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Title of the Report

The Main title of the report is “**Human Resource Planning and Recruitment process of Dan Foods Ltd.**”

Abstract

Human Resource Planning is one of the vital roles for practicing human resource in the organization. Human resource planning determines the current position and human resource requirements in the future perspective. Human Resource Planning is largely based on the concept of people in an organization for implementing strategic decision. It also depicts that there is a significant relationship between the human resource planning and organizational manpower requirements. Human Resource Planning also deals with the broad issues for the employment in order to have organizational effectiveness.

The recruitment process is the first step to make any recruitment strategic advantage for any organization. Moreover, it helps to find out the qualified employees through recruitment process according to the requirement of specific role in any organization. Recruitment and selection are the important operations in the human resource management designed to make the best use of talent to meet up the organizational objectives as a whole. That’s why recruitment practice helps the employee to put into practice how the recruitment strategies are done. Selection is the process of hiring the best people from the alternatives that’s most suitable for the job. The selection is also taken place depends on the qualifications of an employee that match with the organizational job description and job specification.

Keywords: HR Planning, Manpower Forecasting, Recruitment and Selection, organizational factors, organization

1.2 Introduction

Internship is the basic requirements of the BBA Program of the faculty of Business Administration of Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University. After completing all the theoretical course which we have taught in our business subjects is to gain knowledge and experience in professional activities. For this Reason, I got the opportunity of working as a HR Intern at Dan Foods Ltd where I have done my three months tenure Internship. Dan Foods Ltd is a renowned FMCG Industry where many qualified candidates are working as intern to gain practical knowledge. My Internship supervisor Mahmudul Hasan Pias assigned me the topic on Human Resource Planning and recruitment process. It is also expected on this report would be able to portray the importance of HR Practices on Dan Foods Ltd. As part of an organization the HRM must be prepared to deal with the effects of the changing world of work. So, this report helps me to study of the recruitment process, HR Management and the selection process criteria in the context of Dan Foods Ltd.

1.3 Rational of the Report

The overall justification in the report is to focus mainly on the recruitment process and how the Human Resource Planning is done because it links with the internship to get the student to exposed to the job world. For that participating in the corporate job fair program helps me to get the experience on expectation between freshers and employer to adapt all with the recruitment process. The fundamental rational of this report is to get the student to know the theoretical concept into work life experience related on Human Resource.

1.4 Objective of the Report

Based on the two objectives prepare the report: Primary and Secondary objective

1.4.1: Main Objective: The primary focus of this report to gain practical knowledge how the company HRM Planning Practice is done in the organization perspective and also get the necessary information about the procedures on recruitment techniques are followed by the Dan Foods Ltd.

1.4.2: Secondary Objective

- To ensure the effective manpower forecasting in the organization
- To establish and recognizing the future job requirements according to HRP policy
- To ensure effective utilization of work force to meet organizational HRP needs.
- To identify the sources of recruitment process preferred by recruiters for successful recruitment
- To analyze the satisfactory level of employees regarding recruitment and selection
- To ascertain the difficulties faced by the recruiters during recruitment process

1.5 Research Methodology and Analysis

This Report is mainly conducted on a systematic approach and have gathered information from selection of my topic to make the final report. The Data analysis is conducted using a quantitative to analyze the study to prepare structured Interview questionnaire with the total population size is 22 where sample size of 18 employees by using collecting the response from the existing employee working in the organization. The questionnaire consisted two parts, one-part focus on the demographic and second part focus on questionnaire related to the recruitment process. Different pie-chart and column chart are used for data analysis.

Sources of Data

Data Collected from both Primary and Secondary Sources are:

1.5.1: Primary Sources

- Observing the organization overview and gather experience related on HR.
- Interact with my HR Head and my colleagues for collecting information
- Participate in job fair program helps me to gather information

1.5.2: Secondary Sources

- Get to Dan Foods Ltd Website
- Annual Review on Dan Foods Ltd

1.5.3: Methods of Data Collection & Analysis

- **Questionnaire:** Data is gathered by distributing a questionnaire format to the mid-level managers which is a structured with one question with multiple questions.
- **Interview Method:** The study includes obtaining information from the knowledgeable person and it is a unstructured one to articulate individuals and professional in the organization
- **Communicate with HR Lead:** Through working with my HR Head and try to collect data regarding about the human resource planning practice and recruitment process on Dan Foods Ltd.

1.6: Limitations of the Study

- **Limited Time:** It's difficult to collect all the information within 3 months timeframe.
- **Personal Limitations:** Some assumptions were made due to not get much information what needed for the report.

Chapter-2

Overview of the Organization

2.1 Overview of the Company:

Dan Foods Limited is a Denmark – Bangladesh joint venture. Dan Cake A/S, Denmark and Pandugar Limited, Bangladesh joined hands in 2012 with a view to serve the Bangladeshi market with high quality bakery and other ready-to-eat food products. Dan Cake A/S, established in 1931 in Denmark, is the Scandinavian market leader in sales and production of cakes and Swiss Rolls under the brand name of ‘Dan Cake’.

Dan Cake was launched in Bangladesh in 2015. It secures the finest raw materials from the best sources to match global benchmarks in quality. It manufactures the products as per European standard of cleanliness & hygiene under the guidance and supervision of the quality assurance team of Dan Cake A/s, Denmark. The factory is located at Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh equipped with modern technology and machinery. A state-of-the-art lab has been set up at the factory to ensure that right quality is strictly maintained all the time throughout the manufacturing and supply chain processes.

Dan Cake is now available in all the major cities of Bangladesh. A highly qualified, energetic and passionate team is driving the Dan Cake business in Bangladesh with a mission to bring a difference in the country’s food business in terms of taste, choice, quality and hygiene. Dan Foods Ltd is in the process of expanding distribution to neighboring countries and has already made its presence in Nepal and India in a limited scale.

2.2 Corporate Profile

The Corporate information of the Dan Foods Ltd are given in a sequence information below:

Particular	Information
Name of the Company	Dan Foods Ltd
Establishment	1931 In Denmark & Joint Venture Bangladesh 2015
Corporate Headquarters	House-43, Road- 35A(New) 2 nd Floor Gulshan-2, Dhaka 1212
Factory:	Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka
Industry	Food and Beverage Manufacturing
Employee Size	500-1000
Organization Website	dancake.com.bd
Email:	info@dancake.com.bd

Table 2.2 Corporate Profile

2.3 Mission:

Dan cake mission is to build a modern, socially responsible company, approaching customers and local community with respect.

2.3.1 Vision:

To become the best snack choice in the country by offering wide, innovative and tasty options and maintaining global standard of quality in manufacturing.

2.4 Products:

The Products consist of an assortment of the sweetest delicacies, baked with love under professional supervision. The following is a comprehensive list of the wide variety of baked goods that Dan Cake offers are: Muffin cake, swiss roll, layer cake, cookies, classic brownie, plain cake, Pound cake, Fruit cake, Dry Cake, Cupcake, Premium Lachcha, Breez.

2.5 Board of Directors:

The board of directors of Dan foods ltd is composed of Four Members on the top management level headed by a chairman Nazim Uddin Ahmed From Bangladesh and the chairman Erling Eskildsen Chairman of Dan Cake A/S, Denmark. The Director Khondokar Md Towhiduzzaman from Bangladesh and the director from A/S, Denmark Klaus eskildson.

Figure 2.5: Board of Directors

2.6 Organizational Hierarchy

The Hierarchy of the organization organogram of Dan Foods Ltd. are controlled and directed from the top management to low level management. It makes a good relationship with the stakeholders, boards and goals for which the company is cooperated.

Figure 2.6: Organizational Hierarchy

2.7 International Operations

Dan Cake A/S, Denmark is an internationally recognized company and a leading confectionery manufacturer in Europe which is successfully running in several countries. The company has a wide portfolio of “private label” products that are internationally distributed in more than 30 countries.

Being the supplier to major retail chains in the international market, the company achieves around 75% of its revenues through export activities. Germany, France, the UK, Norway, Sweden and Finland are key export markets.

2.8 News and Events

Breakfast Solution: November 12, 2022 (Dhaka): Country’s leading snack brand “Dan Cake” announced the launching of its new product line under the category name “Breakfast Solutions” for Bangladeshi consumers in a press meet held at Pan Pacific Sonargaon hotel today (November 12, 2022). Mr. Firoz Ahmed, Chief Operating Officer of Dan Foods Ltd unveiled the 3 products “Milk Bread, Tortilla Ruti and Croissant” in front of the present journalists.

Art Competition: Dan foods ltd. also include event like art competition in regional areas like cumilla, Bogura and Rajshahi to brand their market in remote areas by arranging competition in different school and colleges.

National Career Fair: Two biggest career fair is arranged by Dan Foods ltd one is national career fair-2019 and BICCI Fair-2018.

Chapter-3

Literature Review

Literature Review

(**Scott, 1994**) define Human Resource planning (HRP) that “it is the process for ensuring that the Human Resources requirements of an organization are identified and plans are made for satisfying those requirements”.

(**Walker, 1980**) according to him, human resource planning is the process of analyzing an organization’s human resource requirements under changing conditions and developing activities necessary to satisfy these needs.

(**Ghosh, 1981**) defined two broad categories of methods for measuring HR planning, the one being systematic methods which include statistical methods, work study and quantitative methods; whereas, the other being the non-systematic methods which include the opinion of managers or head of the departments and imitation of existing practices in similar concern.

According to (**Keep.E, 1989**) the objective of HRM resourcing strategy is to obtain the right basic material in the form of a work force endowed with the appropriate qualities, skills, knowledge and potential for future training. The selection and recruitment of workers best suited to meeting the needs of the organization ought to form a core activity upon which most other HRM policies geared towards development and motivation could be built.

A comparatively detailed study of models in manpower planning is done by (**Edwards J. , 1983**) who explained that the study relevant to manpower planning rest on three pillars. The first pillar is the prediction of future demand of human resource; the second pillar is the prediction of future supply in the human resource; and, the third pillar is about closing the gap between the first and the second pillar and making policies for that. For demand, prediction author highlights the models based on organization output and for supply prediction stock and flow concept.

(**Manzini, 1988**) emphasized that all organizational initiatives need an integration with the HR practices for successfully integrating corporate strategies. When all strategic initiatives i.e. growth, better customers service, innovative production methods, improvements in after sale services, mergers, etc. possess an alignment with HR practices and policies of the organization e.g. with organizing, communicating, developing, appraising, and rewarding employees, and keeping an eye on the future capabilities of the organization, the chances of successful and better resulting implementation of strategic plans increase. The HR practices also need to be aligned with objectives of the organization.

(**Ulrich, 1987**) added that HR planning is recognized as a source of development of organizational functions based on missions and objectives of the business. With the help of planning, areas that need better functioning are identified to make them grow and succeed. “Many HR planning methodologies have been developed and organizations have also crafted their own, most of these methods are similar to those described in the literature like: setting up formal objectives, identifying appropriate organizational strategies and searching for any innovative HR applications”.

(Edwards G. P., 1988)“Human resource planning is particularly important for emerging, rapid-growth and high-tech business. Mature business in need of new products, services, markets, acquisitions or divestitures must also plan to identify, attract or reallocate the talent necessary for revitalization and continued competition”. For satisfying training and career development needs of employees and fulfilling organizational demands, succession planning and organization development occupy an important role. If, in case, the in-house supply of labour is more than needed, this problem of resource rearrangement needs to be dealt with.

Recruitment is the process of discovering or selecting and hiring or best qualified candidate from inside or outside of organization for a job opportunity. The recruitment process includes examining the necessities of work, drawing employee to that occupation, screening and selecting candidates, contracting, and coordinating the new employee to the association. Also, HR department responsible to choose the right person or best qualified candidate for the post for organization needs **(Abdullah N. N., 2019)**

The recruitment is the main function of HR department and the recruitment process is the first step towards making the competitive quality and the recruitment strategic advantage for the association. Recruitment is the process of discovering and catching qualified or appropriate applicant to fill the vacant position **(Anwar, 2021)**

The recruitment process includes examining the necessities of work, drawing employee to that occupation, screening and selecting candidates, contracting, and coordinating the new employee to the association **(Khan, 2019)**

(Abdullah N. N., 2015) Internal recruitment is cost efficient, to support employee satisfaction and moral. Spend some time in the recruitment or Encourage current employees before looking outside the company for talent.

External recruitment in some case it is useful and beneficially like bringing new candidates it brings new skills and new idea for your company but in some case, it has disadvantage like less experiencing because new employee will take too much time to learn rules and points on their job **(Anwar, 2021)**

Selecting process includes a progression of steps to be taken after for picking the suitable employee for the empty position **(Zebari, 2015)**

Similarly, a single brief selection interview might be enough for applicants for lower-level positions, while applicants for managerial jobs might be interviewed by a number of experts **(Ali, 2014)**

Chapter-4

Theoretical Framework on Human Resource Planning And Recruitment process of Dan Foods Ltd

4.1: Human Resource Planning

Economic concept=demand and supply are the context of human resource of any organization.

Human Resource Planning is a process by which human resource are identified, determined and planned that an organization needs in order to meet both its short term and long-term requirements and human resource planning is based on the concept of the people are most important strategic resources of an organization. Planning for human resources is a challenging task today which increases competitive environment labor shortage, changing demographics to protect both employees and the environment That's why DFL always gives special focus on their Human resource planning. DFL always tries to achieve the successful strategies in order to retain employees as an asset for long term relation.

4.2: Human Resource Planning Process:

Human Resource captures all the actions related to human resource planning which involves examining the forecasting employee skills like human resource requirements by projecting present resources into the future requirements through anticipating human resource problem. The human resource planning process are given below:

Figure 4.2: Human Resource Planning Process

- 1) **Determining the objectives of Human Resource Planning:** The objective of human asset arranging is to guarantee the best fit among representatives and occupations, while staying away from labor deficiencies or overflows. Human asset arranging is a sub-arrangement of the all-out hierarchical preparation. It is a necessary piece of corporate arrangement and fills the actual need of association in numerous ways. The basic role of human asset arranging is to plan for the future by decreasing hierarchical vulnerability comparable to the procurement, arrangement, and advancement of workers. HR arranging is finished to accomplish the ideal utilization of HR and to have the right kinds and right number of workers to meet hierarchical objectives.
- 2) **Current Manpower Inventory:** Labor arranging is a vital device and method of human asset the board. It essentially targets keeping up with and working on the capacity of an association to achieve the objectives of an association by creating and using appropriately its HR.
- 3) **Forecasting Demand and Supply:** It helps the company to match with the future employee development with the future supply in order to meet with the organizational available resources which requires future skills for a particular job.
- 4) **Manpower Gaps:** The manpower gaps are analyzed if there is any deficit when they get the deficit then the organization hired new employees depends on the forecasting demand and supply.
- 5) **Employment Plan:** Employment plan is required in every organization to have a proper training to make the employee more knowledgeable to help the employee's productivity which helps the organization to gain more profit.
- 6) **Training and Development:** Employee's training and development need to be ensured in every organization for not only new employee but also existing employee as well. HR planning need to be adequate much ensured for the training facilities.
- 7) **Appraisal of Manpower Planning:** Proper evaluation is conducted by following proper appraisal system which increases the effectiveness of manpower.

4.3: Dan Foods Ltd Human Resource Planning Process

DFL HR Planning process follows only three steps:

- **Future Manpower Forecasting:** At first DFL measure the employee's skills, knowledge, performance appraisal based on it DFL analysis on the future workforce requirements to run the business operations.
- **HR Strategy and Implementation:** DFL also develops HR strategy to review the gaps between HR Supply and demand then sufficient amount of implementation need to create proper manpower forecasting that will help in the future HR demand.
- **Assessing Employee Performance:** DFL tries to control measures set key performance indicator to ensure the accurate number of employee performance that satisfies the HR demand.

4.5: Dan Foods Ltd Benefits of Human Resource Planning

As the HR Planning is a long-term process so it needs require lot of time for brainstorming, analyzing, decision making for the HR to achieve their goals. The benefits of Dan Foods Ltd for the human resource planning which is given below:

- **Organization Manpower Needs:** Human Resource planning is addressed in the DFL recruitment process. Through recruitment process is a time-consuming process like collecting CV, job advertisement, hired new employees and trained new employees as per the organization manpower needs. So, effective planning helps DFL to ensure the business staffing needs.
- **Ensure hiring Right people:** To find out the effective potential candidates from the recruitment process they want to select the right candidates on the basis of 2 tests (written and viva) to ensure most qualified candidates.
- **Training Employees:** Effective training programs is very helpful for the current or new employees. That's why DFL follows a training model for their employees for the benefits of company rules and regulations, duties and responsibilities compensation other things need to know for the employees. That's because DFL create training programs for their employees.
- **Provide Control Measures:** Through proper control measures helps to ensure proper time discipline in the organization which DFL helps to determine accurate number of human resources are working effectively or not.

4.6: Conceptual Framework of Human Resource Planning practice

Figure 5.2: Framework of Human Resource Planning Practice

Research Hypothesis:

H1: There is a significant relationship between the availability of HRP policies and Human resource organizational practice

H2: There is a significant relationship between HRP practice and procedures and Human resource organizational practice

H3: There is a significant relationship between Challenges of implementing HR Policy and Human resource organizational practice

4.7: Recruitment process of Dan Foods Ltd

HR recruitment and selection are very important tool for the DFL to find out the best possible skilled candidates. As an intern tried to learn much about the employee recruitment in DFL as a Internship employee. A responsibility for recruitment process fully depends on the HR department so HR department works to find out the attract qualified candidates. The functions of the recruitment and selection process of DFL are given Below:

Figure 4.7: Recruitment process of Dan Foods Ltd

4.8: Job Analysis

First of all, DFL need to conduct the job analysis first through a systematic approach to collect the required information regarding about the job duties, roles and responsibilities, necessary skills to perform the assigned tasks and duties, working condition and the environment of a job.

4.8.1: Territory Sales Executive Recruitment Process

As an Intern used to work on the recruitment process of Territory Sales Executive for the DFL. Through working with the recruitment process the DFL search candidate for their company to have a basic requirement from the candidates. These types of employees need to perform the task by achieving sales target with his team Sales Representative and distributor in order to maintain a good client relationship to meet the target sales.

4.8.2: Relevant Experience for Territory sales executive

- To achieve monthly sales target
- Creating a high performing team
- Manage DB and Territory sales Management
- Execution and sales software automation'
- DB and SR recruitment & train the team

DFL wants full-time employee for the post. The educational requirement is minimum graduate from any reputed public/private university in any discipline. Experience should have 2+ years of experience in FMCG Sales. Need to be good at MS Office Application, age not more than 30 years. Freshers from public university may apply.

4.9: Sources of CV Collection

A responsibility for recruitment process fully depends on the HR department so HR department works to find out the attract qualified candidates. FL follow some stages to collect CV From Different sources at primary stages. The following process they followed:

4.9.1: Source of Recruitment

In DFL three sources of recruitment are followed.

4.9.2: Sources of Internal Recruitment

- Company Website
- Employee Reference

4.9.3: Sources of External Recruitment

- Jobs website Portal
- Campus Recruitment
- Facebook Job group
- LinkedIn

4.9.4: Daffodil International University Job Fair

Attended 3 days job fair at 01-12-22 to 03-12-22 in DIU. Time period was from 10:00 AM to 4:00 PM. The duties as an Intern employee used to represent DFL and collect CV from fresh graduate those who are interested to apply for the desired position. Try to give information of company details and the relevant job post responsibility, job vacancy and so on.

4.10: DFL Recruitment process and Selection Process

At first need to screen out the CV for both freshers and experience CV and call them for the interview depends on the recruitment circular.

4.10.1: DFL Recruitment and Selection Steps

In DFL 8 Steps are followed on recruitment and selection are given below:

Step 1: Screening and Short-listing Applications

The response was received from the given advertisement of any job circular and cv are collected and screened. The CV as well as the covering letters are judged without cover letters no cv is accepted. Try to screen cv first on public university which gives the highest weights among than the private and national university. Based on the presence of these three factors specially clubbing experience, achievements and computer literacy specially on MS Excel are counted as the cumulative weights of all applicants so these are the special criteria if found on the fresher CV then the candidates are called for the written test.

Step 2: Written Test

DFL always believed that before interview written test is much valuable and useful tool to select the desired candidates. The written test required about the basic knowledge on required fields.

Step 3: Interview

The interview took place between the candidates and HR which follows the elimination method before getting final job offer. The interview time is also given flexible for the shortlisted candidates if he/she working or busy at the time of interview. The candidates were asked to bring cv along with other important documents before attend the interview.

Step 4: Employment Decision

If any candidate selected in the interview then the candidates need to follow HR policy in the organization with the stated terms that mentioned in the final interview so candidates has the right to make decisions regarding about company rules and regulations before getting permanent on the job.

Step 5: Offering the Appointment letter

The candidate is given an offer letter by specifying job duties and responsibilities, salary package that provided by the organization. The candidates always have free discussion with HR if any problem arises.

Step: 6 Induction of a Candidate

After completing all the recruitment process the selected candidates need to be present on the given date of induction program where new candidates are introduced or familiar with the company culture, staff and head of the department

Step: 7 Candidates Documents

The selected candidates are requested to bring all their academic & professional certificates along with the previous job separation or release letter with other related documents.

Step: 8 Placement

After completing all the recruitment process finally placement is done for the new employees.

4.11: Conceptual Framework of Recruitment and Selection

Figure 4.11: Framework of Recruitment and Selection

Research Hypothesis:

H1: There is a significant relationship between the time procedure of recruitment and employee perception regarding recruitment and selection.

H2: There is a significant relationship between the right use of assessment and employee perception regarding recruitment and selection.

H3: There is a significant relationship between gender discrimination and employee perception regarding recruitment and selection.

Chapter-5

Data Analysis and Findings

5.1: Analysis of the Data on Recruitment and Selection

During Internship Period, conduct an informal interview discussion with few responsible employees in different levels or positions such as Finance Accounts, MIS, Branding, Sales and Marketing Department to recognize about the DFL employers' point of view regarding recruitment and selection process of Dan Foods Ltd. Let's have a discuss about the analysis of taking survey about 18 existing DFL Employees:

Gender

Figure: Gender Response

Analysis: The above graph shows about the graph on DFL 88.9% percent male employee and 11.1% females are working in the organization.

Age

Figure: Age in Years

Analysis: The above graph shows about the experience of employees in DFL Group are working. In the analysis it is clear that 27.8% employees working between the age of 20-29. 16.7% of employees have the age 40-49 years, 50% of employees have age between 30-39 years and relatively above 50 years.

Experience

Figure: Experience Working

Analysis: The above graph shows about the experience of working in Dan Foods Ltd employee members. In response to the survey 44.4% are have higher experience 3-5 years. 27.8% employees are between 1-2 years 16.7% are above 5 years' experience and 11.1% only have the experience 0-1 years.

1) Are selection and recruitment process is fair enough?

Figure 1: Recruitment and Selection Fair

Analysis: The above graph shows about the recruitment & selection process of working in Dan Foods Ltd employee members. In response to the survey 55.6% and 22.2% employee are highly agree satisfied with the recruitment process others 16.7% are neutral regarding on it. and few employees are disagreed with recruitment process

2) Does the organization clearly define the position objectives and candidate specifications in recruitment process?

Figure 2: Define Job position in Organization

Analysis: The above graph shows that 33.3% employee highly agree believes that position objectives are clearly defined on recruitment process, but 27.8% shows neutral response 22.2% shows agree on it but 16.7% shows disagree on it.

3) Is the organization doing timeliness recruitment and selection process?

Figure 3: Timeliness Recruitment and Selection

Analysis: According to survey, 55.6% of employees agree and 27.8% are shown highly agree regarding on timeliness of recruitment and selection process.

4) Does the HR Department is efficiency in selection policy of employees?

Figure 4: HR Department Efficiency

Analysis: The above graph shows about the perspective of employees in DFL responses to the inquiry that 38.9% shows both neutral and disagree in the selection policy of employees and other 11.1% shows both agree and highly agree employee thinks it doesn't work out to find out best candidates according selection policy.

5) Selection and recruitment procedures helps to find deserved candidate according to required position?

Figure 5: Selection and Recruitment procedures

Analysis: The above graph shows that 33.3% are highly agree on regarding on recruitment procedures on finding deserved candidate. 27.8% shows agree on it 11.1% shows both neutral and highly disagree on it and 16.7% are disagree on this recruitment and selection procedures.

6) Employee's experience and skills matters more than educational background in case of hiring?

Figure 6: Employee Experience and Skills in Hiring

Analysis: The above graph shows that 38.9% employees are highly agree and 11.1% shows agree on regarding employee's experience is more matters than educational background. 33.3% shows neutral and 16.7% employees shows disagree on it.

7) Is there any discrimination throughout selection and recruitment procedure?

Figure 7: Discrimination Male and Female

Analysis: The above graph shows that 38.9% employees believe yes there is no discrimination on recruitment procedure but 33.3% shows agree and 11.1% are shown highly agree and 11.1% are neutral.

8) How would you rate the HR department's performance in recruitment and selection?

Figure 8: HR department Performance

Analysis: The above graph shows that 38.9% shows agree and 27.8% are highly agree employees rate HR department performance are much satisfactory process none other 22.2% are neutral and 11.1% shows disagree approach on HR is doing effectiveness of the interviewing process.

9) Rate the effectiveness of the interviewing process and other selection instruments, such as testing?

Figure 9: Interview and Recruitment Instruments

Analysis: The above graph shows that 55.6% shows highly agree on effectiveness on interviewing process and other selection method and 16.7% are shown agree and 16.7% are neutral regarding on it and 11.1% are disagree on interviewing selection method.

10) How effective is Human Resource Planning (HRP) policies and practices in Dan foods Ltd?

Figure 10: Effective on HRP IN DFL

Analysis: The above graph shows that 44.4% are agree on HR planning policy regulated on dan foods ltd. 27.8% are neutral regarding on this point 16.7% are highly agree and 11.1% are disagree on HR planning policy.

11) Does your organization follow a formal system in the Human Resource Planning?

Figure 11: Formal System HRP

Analysis: The above graph shows that 27.8% are shown highly agree and 22.2% are disagree on formal system regulated in HR Planning but 27.8% shows neutral and 27.8% are agree on the human resource planning policy.

12) Are you satisfied with the manner human resource planning has been practiced in the organization over the last 8 years?

Figure 12: Satisfied on HRP Practice

Analysis: The above graph shows that 27.8% are agree, 27.8% are neutral and 27.8% employees are disagreeing on satisfied related on HR planning practice in last 8 years.

13) Do you think that these constraints and challenges impact on human resource planning in the organization?

Figure 13: Challenges impact on HRP

Analysis: The above graph shows that 33.3% showed neutral and 33.3% are disagree on these challenges that impact on human resource planning in organization but 27.8% shown highly agree that HR have overcome the challenges on HR planning in organization.

14) Do you observe or experience any challenges hindering human resource planning in the organization?

Figure 14: Observing on Hindrance on HRP

Analysis: The above graph shows that 38.9% employees are shown agree on having experience related on HR planning 27.8% are highly agree on it while other 16.7% are disagree on this point and 11.1% are neutral

15) How do you rate the impact of these constraints and challenges on human resource planning in the organization?

Figure 15: Constraints and challenges on HRP

Analysis: The above graph shows that 44.4% are neutral no comments on impact on these constraints and challenge 16.7% are agree on it 22.2% are highly agree on the impact challenges and last 16.7% are disagree on it.

5.2: Findings

The analysis found through the survey on existing employees regarding recruitment and selection the findings are discussed below:

- DFL mainly focus on hiring male workers as opposed to other females once.
- The employees feel that their personal experience capabilities are matter more than the educational qualifications
- The payment system in the company is much pleasant get total compensation within the first week of month.
- DFL mainly focus on quality employee rather than quantity skilled employee which helps the company to work more effectively.
- The HR Department is also very kind to the respective employees
- In terms of policy Bangladesh labor leave laws are regulated in DFL but need to follow the company policy according to HR rules.
- DFL have lacking in assisting training programs in every month for the existing employees to keep motivate
- Need to focus on Sales representative employees and monitor need to be ensured to achieve sales target

Chapter-6

Recommendation & Conclusion

6.1 Recommendation

In DFL there are few things that need to be change and some issued need to be improved according to the above findings of the report, the following recommendation can be given for the betterment of Dan Foods Ltd. So, the following list of recommendation can be considered that need to be improved:

- DFL don't promote their brand and don't give focus on the marketing activity should introduce new type of talents acquisition to recruit skilled talent expertise.
- DFL need to mentor their employees to reduce employee turnover rate.
- DFL need to provide promotion after proper evaluation on performance appraisal in timely manner to reduce turnover rate.
- In DFL the number of HR team is very low in terms of sales team. The total number of employees in DFL corporate office is 15 among them only 2 employees is HR. So, DFL need to focus on expansion for the HR Team to have an effective workforce.
- DFL need to provide training for the development of employees which increases the satisfaction of level of all levels of employees.
- DFL need to focus on the performance appreciation work in each month to motivate employees.

6.2 Conclusion

First of all, it's an honor for selecting me as an intern for Dan Foods Ltd one of the leading pioneers FMCG business Industry. The HR planning process and working with the direct recruitment procedures also helped me to give more attention on Human resource activities to the organizational plans and objectives.

To be successful and give much effort, dedication towards through the organization Human Resource Management is needed so the HR activities need to set some dynamic plans and for implementing the today's business world.

It was a good professional experience through working with DFL which helps me in terms of professionally in the workplace which cherish my moment of working at various works related to HR and gained knowledge from the company.

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Appendix (A)

Survey Questionnaire for Recruitment process in Dan Foods Ltd.

Gulshan-2, Dhaka.

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Department of Human Resource Management

Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University

General Profile of Respondent:

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Age (Years): 23-27 28-32 38-42 43-50 51-60
3. Experience: 0-1-year 1-2-year 3-5 year Above 5 year

Questionnaire:

Sl. No	Statements	Highly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Highly Agree
1	Are selection and recruitment process being fair enough?	-	-	16.7%	55.6%	22.2%
2	Does the organization clearly define the position objectives and candidate specifications in recruitment process?	-	16.7%	27.8%	22.2%	33.3%
3	Is the organization doing timeliness recruitment and selection process?	-	-	-	55.6%	27.8%
4	Does the HR Department is efficiency in selection policy of employees?	-	38.9%	38.9%	11.1%	11.1%
5	Selection and recruitment procedures helps to find deserved candidate according to required position?	-	16.7%	11.1%	27.8%	33.3%
6	Employee's experience and skills matters more than educational background in case of hiring?	-	16.7%	33.3%	11.1%	38.9%

Sl. No	Statements	Highly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Highly Agree
7	Is there any discrimination throughout selection and recruitment procedure?	-	38.9%	11.1%	33.3%	11.1%
8	How would you rate the HR department's performance in recruitment and selection?	-	11.1%	22.2%	38.9%	27.8%
9	Rate the effectiveness of the interviewing process and other selection instruments, such as testing?	-	11.1%	16.7%	16.7%	55.6%
10	How effective is Human Resource Planning (HRP) policies and practices in Dan foods Ltd?	-	11.1%	27.8%	44.4%	16.7%
11	Does your organization follow a formal system in the Human Resource Planning?	-	22.2%	27.8%	27.8%	22.2%
12	Are you satisfied with the manner human resource planning has been practiced in the organization over the last 8 years?	-	27.8%	27.8%	27.8%	16.7%
13	Do you think that these constraints and challenges impact on human resource planning in the organization?	-	33.3%	33.3%	-	27.8%
14	Do you observe or experience any challenges hindering human resource planning in the organization?	-	16.7%	11.1%	38.9%	27.8%
15	How do you rate the impact of these constraints and challenges on human resource planning in the organization?	-	16.7%	44.4%	16.7%	22.2%